

1 **Mature Nitrifying Biofilters Counteract Invasion by Rapid-Growing**
2 **Heterotrophic Bacteria in Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS)**

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8 **Highlights**

- 9 • Mature biofilters strongly reduced invasion success by rapid-growing
10 heterotrophic bacteria in RAS.
- 11 • *Gammaproteobacteria* were less abundant in systems with mature biofilters.
- 12 • Biofilter disinfection increased invasion success and promoted rapid-growing
13 heterotrophic bacteria.
- 14 • Biofilter perturbation, like disinfection, entails a risk for suboptimal microbial
15 environments in RAS.

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16 **Abstract**

17 Nitrifying biofilters are essential components in recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS)
18 to perform nitrification. Beyond this primary function, their contribution to maintaining a
19 stable, healthy microbial environment for fish remains underappreciated. We previously
20 hypothesized that mature biofilters would resist bacterial invasions and limit rapid-growing
21 heterotrophic bacteria. We performed two experiments to test this hypothesis: first, in
22 small-scale RAS with Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) fry, and second, in laboratory-scale
23 moving bed bioreactors (MBBRs). Two treatment groups were compared: systems with a
24 mature biofilter (control) or with a perturbed biofilter induced by disinfection with hydrogen
25 peroxide. The systems were then challenged by introducing four strains representing
26 rapid-growing heterotrophic bacteria: *Flavobacterium* sp., *Proteus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp.,
27 and *Psychrobacter* sp. Microbial communities of biomediated-biofilm and water were
28 analyzed using 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing (Illumina). For both experiments,
29 we found that microbial communities in the biofilm and water of perturbed systems had
30 substantially higher relative abundances of these strains eight days after their addition,
31 indicating significantly greater invasion success ($p < 0.01$). Furthermore, the perturbed
32 systems showed significantly higher relative abundances of *Gammaproteobacteria* and
33 *Flavobacteriia* ($p < 0.01$), classes of which encompass many genera associated with
34 opportunistic bacteria and fish pathogens. Our findings emphasize that the biofilter is
35 crucial for optimizing the microbial environment in RAS by counteracting invasion and
36 suppressing unfavorable bacterial growth. Understanding the negative consequences of
37 biofilter perturbation on the microbial environment in the system, beyond nitrification, is
38 crucial for developing effective management strategies in RAS.

39 **Keywords:** Biosecurity; K-selection; Microbial quality; Microbiome; R-selection

40 1. Introduction

41 A nitrifying biofilter is an indispensable component of recirculating aquaculture systems
42 (RAS). Its most recognized function is the nitrification, a microbial conversion of toxic
43 ammonia (NH_3) to nitrate (NO_3^-), thus maintaining these compounds at low concentrations
44 in the system. In addition to nitrification, the biofilter can directly and indirectly influence
45 the rearing-water microbiota. The direct influence occurs via the continuous shedding of
46 the bio-media-biofilm due to overdensity, biofilm aging, friction among the bio-media,
47 aeration, and water agitation. The shed biofilm constitutes a substantial fraction of
48 suspended particulates circulating in the RAS, as demonstrated by an isotope tracer study
49 (Franco-Nava et al., 2004). This shedding is particularly prominent in the moving-bed
50 biofilter (Fernandes et al., 2017). On the other hand, the indirect influence occurs through
51 microbial conversions in the biofilter, which affect the water chemistry and consequently
52 the selection pressure on the water microbiota (Rojas-Tirado et al., 2019). The
53 consumption of easily degradable organic substrate, particularly the dissolved fraction, by
54 a substantial biomass of heterotrophic bacteria in the biofilter is of particular interest. By
55 lowering the dissolved organic substrates available for microbial growth in the rearing
56 water, the biofilters increase resource competition. This creates less favorable conditions
57 for the rapid-growing heterotrophic bacteria, i.e., r-strategists in the system (Fossmark et
58 al., 2020; Vadstein et al., 2018). The close and continuous contact between water
59 microbiota and fish may shape the fish-associated microbiota itself (Bakke et al., 2015;
60 Bugten et al., 2022; Deng et al., 2022), and ultimately, the fish's performance (Vestrum et
61 al., 2018). This cascading effect suggests that the biofilter can contribute to maintaining a
62 beneficial microbial environment for fish, i.e., reducing detrimental microbial-host
63 interactions, thereby improving fish health and welfare. This ecological role of the biofilter
64 has received less attention and is less frequently addressed in RAS research.

65 In commercial RAS, the biofilter is often subjected to various perturbations, such as
66 disinfection and washing. Biofilter disinfection is occasionally implemented in RAS when
67 issues such as persistently unstable nitrification and disease outbreaks occur. There is
68 concern that the biofilm in the biofilters served as a reservoir for pathogenic bacteria
69 (Blancheton et al., 2013). Total disinfection of the biofilter and the entire system following
70 each fish production cycle is therefore considered one of several methods to prevent
71 disease outbreaks. RAS operators, researchers, and regulatory authorities debated
72 whether this regular biofilter disinfection was an appropriate countermeasure to reduce
73 disease outbreaks (Jensen, 2022). One rationale for regular disinfection is to mitigate the
74 disease risks by substantially reducing bacterial loads, including pathogens, in the biofilter.
75 While disinfection aims to eliminate pathogens, the process is inherently nonselective and
76 affects all bacteria, including guilds beneficial to the system, such as nitrifiers (Møller et
77 al., 2010). Microbial ecological theory then predicts that reducing bacterial numbers, for
78 example, through disinfection without lowering the carrying capacity, would cause fewer
79 bacteria to compete for space and nutrients, thereby creating a less competitive
80 environment with more available open niches (Attramadal et al., 2021). Communities in
81 such condition are hypothesized to be more vulnerable to bacterial invasions (De Schryver
82 and Vadstein, 2014) and would be dominated by the rapid-growing heterotrophic bacteria
83 (Vadstein et al., 2018), many of which are potentially opportunistic and detrimental to fish.
84 This hypothesis, however, has not yet been experimentally validated. Furthermore, to the

85 best of our knowledge, no study has investigated the impact of biofilter perturbation by
86 disinfection on microbial environment in RAS, particularly regarding the risk of invasion by
87 fast-growing heterotrophic bacteria strains and the overall community succession in the
88 biofilm and water following the disinfection.

89 In this study, we investigated the positive but underappreciated role of the biofilter in
90 maintaining a healthy microbial environment for fish in RAS. We hypothesized that a well-
91 functioning and mature RAS biofilter would counteract the invasion by rapid-growing
92 heterotrophic bacteria by maintaining high competition for organic substrates. This strong
93 competition would also be expected to suppress the rapid growth of potentially harmful
94 opportunistic bacteria. Conversely, a perturbed RAS biofilter would increase invasion
95 success and favor the rapid proliferation of heterotrophic bacteria. Given this critical but
96 less appreciated role of the biofilter in maintaining positive microbial environments, the
97 new knowledge generated in this study is essential for optimizing microbial management
98 in the system.

99 **2. Materials and methods**

100 **Overview of the experimental design**

101 To test the hypothesis that a well-functioning RAS biofilter counteracts invasion and limits
102 the rapid proliferation of heterotrophic bacteria, we used an experimental design where
103 we perturbed the biofilter function by disinfecting the biomedica. This was followed by the
104 introduction of four rapid-growing heterotrophic bacterial strains into the system and the
105 assessment of their colonization success in the water and in biofilms. We performed two
106 experiments based on this approach in two complementary experimental systems as
107 follows: First, we conducted an experiment in two identical small-scale RAS with Atlantic
108 salmon (*Salmo salar*) fry (hereafter referred to as Exp1; Fig. 1A). The experimental design
109 included two treatments: one RAS had a mature biofilter serving as a control, and the other
110 had a biofilter with biomedica that had recently been disinfected with hydrogen peroxide
111 (H₂O₂, as detailed below). The second invasion experiment was conducted using a set of
112 semicontinuous moving-bed bioreactors (MBBRs), with the same experimental groups as
113 in Exp1 (hereafter referred to as Exp2; Fig. 1B). Shortly after the disinfection, all
114 experimental systems in both experiments were challenged by introducing four selected
115 bacterial strains, representing rapid-growing heterotrophic bacteria, hereafter referred to
116 as invaders (for details on strain selection, see below). In addition, before performing
117 Exp1, we conducted a batch experiment to evaluate the impact of different disinfectant
118 concentrations on reducing nitrification capacity. Because disinfection is expected to
119 reduce nitrification capacity, this evaluation was crucial in preventing ammonia toxicity in
120 Exp1, where fish were present.

121 **Fig. 1** Schematic setup of the experimental systems used in this study. A) Design of the small-
 122 scale RAS used in Exp1, manufactured by Spranger Kunststoffe GmbH, DE. The water flowed out
 123 from the three rearing tanks through the bottom outlet, then passed through a mechanical filtration
 124 (mesh filter, 200 μm), then to the moving-bed biofilter and sump before being pumped back into
 125 the tanks. A trickling filter (degasser) and a heating-chilling pump were installed in the sump as
 126 the side loops. The rearing tanks were modified to round tanks before the experiment, and the UV
 127 lamp was intentionally deactivated during the experiment to avoid confounding removal of
 128 introduced bacteria. B) Setup of the semicontinuous moving bed bioreactor used in Exp2. C) The
 129 reactor setup used to evaluate the biomedium's nitrification capacity.

130 Selection and preparation of bacteria (invaders) for the invasion experiments

131 The bacterial strains used in the invasion experiments originated from our in-house strain
 132 collection and were isolated from healthy Atlantic salmon yolk-sac fry reared in RAS. The
 133 initial selection criteria were based on their taxonomic classification within bacterial taxa
 134 known to represent rapid-growing bacteria. The strains *Pseudomonas* sp. 3.129,
 135 *Psychrobacter* sp. 3.78, *Proteus* sp. 3.129, and *Flavobacterium* sp. 3.92 were isolated and
 136 taxonomically assigned as described in Fiedler et al (2023). The sources of the isolates
 137 were the skin (*Proteus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Flavobacterium* strains) and the gut
 138 (*Psychrobacter* strain). By Norwegian animal welfare regulations, the use of pathogenic
 139 strains is restricted to designated experimental facilities due to biosecurity concerns. To
 140 ensure that the strains were not specific pathogens, their 16S rRNA gene sequences
 141 (**Supplementary material 1**) were analyzed using the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
 142 (BLAST) on the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) website. The strains
 143 were checked against the 16S rRNA gene of *P. anguilliseptica*, *F. psychrophilum*, and *F.*
 144 *spartansii*, while there is limited evidence for *Psychrobacter* spp. and *Proteus* spp. being
 145 specific pathogens in salmonids.

146 Validation of the bacterial strains' ability to colonize biomedium

147 We evaluated the strain's ability to colonize biomedium with a simple incubation experiment.
 148 Conical flasks (2 L) containing sterile biomedium were used, with 200 mL of tap water and
 149 3 g/L of crushed fish feed as a nutrient source. The flasks were then autoclaved. Each
 150 bacterial candidate was then introduced at two concentration levels: either 10^3 colony
 151 forming unit (CFU)/mL or 10^5 CFU/mL, respectively. For each strain, one flask was used
 152 for each concentration, resulting in a total of eight flasks. Two sterile control flasks
 153 containing only tryptic soy broth (TSB) medium or crushed were included to confirm
 154 sterility throughout the workflow. To prepare the bacteria, frozen glycerol stock of each
 155 strain was streaked onto tryptic soy agar (TSA). Single colonies were selected and sub-
 156 cultured to ensure purity, and their morphological characteristics were recorded

157 **(Supplementary 2)**. To ease the determination of bacterial densities, the relationship
158 between colony-forming units (CFU) and optical density (OD₆₀₀) was established in
159 advance for each strain. Briefly, overnight cultures in TSB were serially diluted, plated on
160 TSA, and the optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) of each dilution was measured. CFU were
161 then plotted against OD, and a linear regression was fitted. To introduce the bacteria into
162 the flasks, the harvest volume was determined based on the number of colonies required
163 and the culture density, as determined by the CFU-OD relationship (**Supplementary**
164 **material 2**). The overnight culture of each strain was harvested by centrifugation at 6,000
165 rpm and 4°C for 10 min. The culture was then washed with sterile phosphate-buffered
166 saline (PBS) to remove the residue of LB or TSB medium, followed by another
167 centrifugation step. The washed bacterial pellets were resuspended in sterile PBS and
168 then introduced into the flask.

169 Flasks were aseptically incubated for eight days at 12°C in a thermoshaker at 155 rpm.
170 On day 8, the biomedica were collected, washed twice with ultrapure water, and transferred
171 into sterile tubes containing glass beads (1 mm) and ultrapure water. Biomedica biofilm was
172 then vortexed at 3,000 rpm for 2 minutes. The biofilm suspension was diluted in series
173 and plated on TSA, incubated for 24–48 hours, and then the CFU on the plates were
174 enumerated. To verify the identity of growing bacteria on the TSA, full-length 16S rRNA
175 genes were amplified from colonies obtained from each treatment using primer Eub-8F
176 (5'-AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG-3') and 1492R (5'-TACGGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT-
177 3'). The PCR master mix composition and cycling conditions are provided in **Appendix A**.
178 The PCR products were visualized via agarose gel electrophoresis, purified using the
179 QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, USA), and then submitted for Sanger sequencing
180 (Eurofins Scientific SE, LUX). These strains exhibited rapid growth on the agar plates and
181 the ability to colonize the virgin biomedica.

182 **Evaluation of nitrification capacity after biomedica disinfection**

183 Batch reactors were used to evaluate the surface-specific oxidation rate of ammonium
184 (NH₄-N; AOR) and nitrite (NO₂-N; NOR). Biomedica (RK Bioelements, DK; specific surface
185 area = 750 m² m⁻³) were sourced from a mature moving-bed biofilter operating in a
186 commercial freshwater RAS for Atlantic salmon smolt production in mid-Norway. The
187 biofilter had been continuously operated for fish production for more than 10 years without
188 disinfection. Upon collection, the biomedica were transported to the laboratory and
189 maintained in ammonium medium (see **Appendix B** for composition) until used in the
190 experiment. The reactor setup is illustrated in

191 **Fig. 1C**. Briefly, each 1 L reactor was filled with an equal number of biofilm carriers (56
192 pieces) and 650 mL of medium containing either ammonium (10 mg/L) for AOR
193 measurement or nitrite (5 mg/L) for NOR measurement (**Appendix B**). Reactors were
194 maintained at 12°C using a chiller and supplied with humidified aeration.

195 To evaluate the effect of disinfection on AOR, biomedica were subjected to different
196 concentrations of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂; Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Four disinfection
197 concentrations were tested: 0 mg/L (control), 300 mg/L, 600 mg/L, and 1,200 mg/L. The
198 biomedica were immersed in the respective disinfection solutions for three hours, then
199 transferred to reactors similar to those above (

200 **Fig. 1C**), which contained medium with ammonium at 10 mg/L.

201 Water samples were collected from the reactors at regular intervals and were filtered
202 through 0.2- μm membrane filters. The concentrations of the nitrogenous compounds were
203 quantified using the Hach® LCK Cuvette Test System on a DR3900 VIS benchtop
204 spectrophotometer (Hach, USA). The raw data showing the measurements of the
205 nitrogenous compounds are provided in **Supplementary material 3**. Linear regression
206 analysis was used to determine the volumetric oxidation rate of ammonium and nitrite (S),
207 equal to the negative regression slope. The surface-specific oxidation rate was calculated
208 using the formula below, following Kinyage and Pedersen et al. (2019).

$$209 \quad \text{AOR (g N m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}) = \frac{S_{\text{ammonium}} \times V_m \times 60 \text{ (min h}^{-1}) \times 24 \text{ (h d}^{-1})}{A_m \times 1000 \text{ (mg g}^{-1})}$$

$$210 \quad \text{NOR (g N m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}) = \frac{S_{\text{nitrite}} \times V_m \times 60 \text{ (min h}^{-1}) \times 24 \text{ (h d}^{-1})}{A_m \times 1000 \text{ (mg g}^{-1})}$$

211 Where, S_{ammonium} is the volumetric ammonium oxidation rate ($\text{mg N L}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$), S_{nitrite} is the
212 volumetric nitrite oxidation rate ($\text{mg N L}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$), V_m is the volume of the medium (L), and
213 A_m is the total surface area of biofilm carriers (m^2).

214 We targeted the H_2O_2 concentration that reduced the surface-specific ammonium
215 oxidation rate by approximately 80 % relative to the control with non-disinfected biomed
216 for use in the invasion experiment in RAS (Exp1). This threshold was chosen to retain
217 significant biomass inactivation while maintaining sufficient ammonium oxidation capacity
218 to prevent ammonia toxicity in fish.

219 **Exp1: Invasion experiment in small-scale RAS**

220 The Exp1 was conducted as part of a master's thesis, and the experiment and preliminary
221 results were described in Hofstad (2023). The experiment was approved by the Norwegian
222 Food Safety Authority (FOTS ID No. 29715). A total of 1,000 Atlantic salmon fry were
223 obtained from a commercial smolt producer in Heim, Norway, and transported in sealed,
224 oxygenated bags by road to the NTNU SeaLab in Trondheim. Upon arrival, the fish were
225 acclimatized for 54 days in a flow-through system. During this period, they were hand-fed
226 twice daily, in the morning and afternoon. We employed two identical small-scale RAS for
227 the experiment, where one system was operated with a biofilter filled with mature control
228 biomed, and the other used the same type of biomed but recently disinfected by
229 immersion in a 300 mg/L hydrogen peroxide bath for 3 hours as described above. These
230 systems are hereafter referred to as "Cont_RAS" and "Disf_RAS", respectively. To assess
231 the colonization potential of the introduced bacterial strains on uncolonized biomed, the
232 autoclaved biomed (VBm) were included in the biofilters of both systems. These VBm
233 were distinguishable from the other biomed in the respective biofilter by cable marking.

234 To acclimatize the fish to the experimental conditions, two days before the experiment,
235 105 salmon fry (average weight of 13.5 grams) were stocked in three rearing tanks in each
236 RAS. On day 0 of the experiment (D0), the freshly harvested bacterial strains, kept in PBS
237 solution (prepared as described above), were introduced into the sump of each RAS at a
238 final concentration of approximately 1.25×10^5 cells/mL per strain. To achieve an
239 appropriate bacterial cell density, the cell number-OD relationship was established in

240 advance by correlating OD₆₀₀ with cell counts obtained via our in-house Attune NxT flow
 241 cytometry (Thermo Fisher, USA) (**Supplementary materials 2**). Briefly, bacterial culture
 242 with known OD was diluted in 0.22- μ m filtered PBS, then stained with SYBR Green I (1 \times
 243 final), and incubated at room temperature in the dark for 10 min. Events were acquired on
 244 the flow cytometry equipped with blue (488 nm, 50 mW) and yellow (561 nm, 50 mW)
 245 lasers. Measurements on dye-only blanks (PBS) were performed. Detector voltages and
 246 gating were optimized for each strain. Cell concentration was calculated as: Cells mL⁻¹ =
 247 (Events in cell gate per μ L) \times 1,000 \times Dilution factor. Measurements were replicated until
 248 the events in the cell gate stabilized.

249 Eight days after introducing the four strains (D8), we ended the experiment. Throughout
 250 the experimental period, fish were continuously fed a formulated diet (EWOS, Cargill) via
 251 automatic feeders (Fish Mate F14, UK) at a rate of approximately 1.5 % of biomass per
 252 day. The photoperiod was maintained at 24 hours of light. To ensure optimal fish welfare,
 253 fish were monitored twice daily for feeding activity and behavioral indicators, including
 254 swimming patterns and opercular movement. Water quality (dissolved oxygen,
 255 temperature, pH) was monitored twice daily. Nitrogen species (total ammonia, nitrite,
 256 nitrate) and alkalinity were analyzed every second day using a colorimetric kit (API, USA).
 257 A recirculation rate of 95 % was targeted, with a planned daily water exchange of 8 L,
 258 representing 5 % of the total system volume. However, on Day 1, 30 L of water was added
 259 to compensate for a minor leakage. Both systems always received identical water
 260 exchange volumes throughout the experiment to maintain consistency between the two
 261 RAS. Technical specifications of the RAS systems are provided in **Table 1**.

262 **Table 1**

263 Technical specifications of the small-scale RAS used in this study.

Parameter	Value
Number of fish per tank	35 individuals \times 3 tanks
Total system volume (including tanks)	~165 L
Tank volume	35 L
Tank hydraulic retention time	15 –30 min
Biofilter volume, biomedica volume (filling rate)	45 L, 17.5 L (38%)
Daily water exchange, recirculation rate (% of total system)	8 L/day, 95 %
Water reuse (L/kg feed)	~530

264 **Exp2: Invasion experiment in semicontinuous moving-bed bioreactors**

265 In Exp2, two treatment groups were established, each consisting of four replicates of
 266 moving-bed bioreactors (MBBRs). The first bioreactor group received mature, untreated
 267 biomedica serving as the control, and the other group received biomedica disinfected with
 268 15 mL of 35 % hydrogen peroxide diluted in 5 L of water (final concentration ~1,200 ppm)
 269 for 3 hours. These systems are hereafter referred to as “Cont_MBBR” and “Disf_MBBR”,
 270 respectively. The bioreactors consisted of laboratory bottles (2 L capacity) filled with 1.8 L
 271 of tap water and 125 pieces of biomedica (**Fig. 1B**).

272 The bioreactors were maintained in a temperature-controlled room at approximately 14–
 273 15 °C. Each bioreactor was aerated using an air stone supplied with filtered air to ensure
 274 proper mixing of the biomedica. Regulators were installed in each air hose to ensure
 275 uniform mixing across bioreactors. On day 0 (D0), all bioreactors running with the
 276 respective biomedica were challenged with the four bacterial strains as described for Exp1.

277 Freshly harvested cultures (prepared as described above) were added to a final
278 concentration of approximately 1.25×10^5 cells/mL for each strain. To provide about 10 %
279 water replacement per day, 100 mL of bioreactor water was replaced twice daily at 09:00
280 and 17:30, with a defined replacement medium consisting of 18 mL of ammonium medium
281 (1 g N L^{-1}), 3 mL of $10\times$ trace elements solution (**Appendix B**), 10 mL of $10\times$ M65 medium,
282 and 69 mL of tap water (**Appendix C**). The replacement medium was prepared daily in a
283 single container and distributed evenly among bioreactors to ensure consistency across
284 replicates. Similar to Exp1, the experiment ended eight days after the introduction of the
285 bacterial strains (D8).

286 **Sample collection and preparation of amplicon sequencing library**

287 For microbial community analysis, biomedica (Bm), bioreactor water (W), RAS tank water
288 (TW), and virgin biomedica (VBm) were collected at two time points: day 0 (D0) and day 8
289 (D8) in both Exp1 and Exp2. On D0, biomedica were collected before the addition of
290 bacterial strains from RAS biofilters (Exp1) or bioreactors (Exp2) immediately after the
291 disinfection. The water samples were collected from tanks (Exp1) 3 hours after the
292 bacterial strains were added to the system, and from bioreactors (Exp2) immediately after
293 the addition. For sampling biomedica-biofilm microbiota, biomedica were retrieved from the
294 RAS biofilters and MBBRs using sterile, long tweezers, then rinsed thoroughly with
295 ultrapure water to remove potential water-suspended bacteria. The biomedica were
296 subsequently cut into smaller pieces using sterile scissors. For sampling water microbiota,
297 approximately 100 mL of water was filtered through a $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ membrane filter (Merck
298 Millipore, DE), and the filter containing the retained biomass was collected. All collected
299 samples were transferred into 2 mL tubes pre-filled with 0.1 mm silica beads for
300 subsequent bead-beating (see below). Samples were immediately transported on dry ice
301 and stored at $-80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until further analysis. Detailed information on sample types, collection
302 time points, and replication is provided in **Supplementary material 4**.

303 DNA was extracted from the water and biomedica samples by using the ZymoBIOMICS™
304 96 MagBead DNA Kit (Zymo Research) on the KingFisher™ Flex Purification System
305 (Thermo Fisher Scientific), following the manufacturer's protocol. The lysis step was
306 performed prior to the DNA extraction by bead-beating the samples in the homogenization
307 tubes (5500 rpm, two cycles of 30 seconds with 15-second intervals between cycles) in
308 $550 \mu\text{L}$ of lysis buffer using the Precellys® 24 cell homogenizer (Bertin Instruments, FRA).
309 The V3–V4 regions of the bacterial 16S rRNA gene were amplified using primers “III-
310 341.F” ($5\text{'-CCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG-3'}$) and “III-805.R”
311 ($5\text{'GACTACNVGGGTATCTAAKCC-3'}$), both equipped with Illumina adapter sequences.
312 Each PCR reaction ($25 \mu\text{L}$ total volume) contained $1 \mu\text{L}$ of DNA template, 0.2 mM of each
313 dNTP (VWR), 0.3 mM of each primer, $0.02 \text{ U}/\mu\text{L}$ of Phusion High-Fidelity DNA
314 Polymerase, and $1\times$ HF Phusion buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). For Exp1, PCRs
315 were performed with pre-denaturation at $98 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 120 seconds, followed by 36
316 thermocycles ($98 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 seconds, $55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 seconds, and $72 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 seconds) and
317 final elongation at $72 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 300 seconds. For Exp2, PCRs were performed with pre-
318 denaturation at $98 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 45 seconds, followed by 28 thermocycles ($98 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 seconds,
319 $58 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 seconds, and $72 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 seconds) and final elongation at $72 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 300
320 seconds.

321 Amplicons ($5 \mu\text{L}$) were assessed by agarose gel electrophoresis and then normalized and
322 purified using the SequalPrep Normalization Plate Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific),

323 according to the manufacturer's instructions. Dual-combinatory indexing of the purified
324 amplicons was performed using the Nextera XT Index Kit v2 (Illumina, USA). Indexing
325 PCR reactions (25 μ L total volume) were performed using 2.5 μ L of normalized PCR
326 product as template, 2.5 μ L of each index, in addition to dNTP, polymerase, and buffer at
327 the concentrations in the final reaction mix as described for the first round of PCR. For
328 Exp1, indexing PCRs were conducted with pre-denaturation at 98 $^{\circ}$ C for 120 s, followed
329 by 15 thermocycles (98 $^{\circ}$ C for 15 s, 55 $^{\circ}$ C for 20 s, and 72 $^{\circ}$ C for 20 s) and final elongation
330 at 72 $^{\circ}$ C for 300 s. For Exp2, indexing PCRs were conducted with pre-denaturation at 98
331 $^{\circ}$ C for 45 s, followed by seven thermocycles (98 $^{\circ}$ C for 45 s, 58 $^{\circ}$ C for 15 s, and 72 $^{\circ}$ C for
332 20 s) and final elongation at 72 $^{\circ}$ C for 300 s. All PCRs were performed using the T100™
333 Thermal Cycler (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc., USA). For each indexed amplicon, ($v = 20 \mu$ L)
334 was normalized and purified again as described above. The amplicons were then pooled
335 and concentrated using Amicon Ultra 0.5 mL centrifugal filters 30 k (Merck & Co., Inc.,
336 USA). Libraries from Exp1 and Exp2 were sequenced separately in two paired-end
337 Illumina MiSeq (2 \times 300 bp) sequencing runs with reagent kit v3 (Illumina, Inc., USA). All
338 amplicon sequencing data are available at NCBI with an accession number of
339 PRJNA1298933. The associated metadata describing the sample type, treatment group,
340 and other relevant information are provided in **Supplementary material 5**.

341 **Processing of amplicon sequencing data**

342 The sequencing reads were processed using USEARCH v11 (Edgar, 2010), following the
343 recommended pipeline by the developer. Briefly, reads were truncated at the first base
344 with a quality score (Q) below 30, then merged, and primer binding sites were removed.
345 The merged reads were quality-filtered and dereplicated to obtain unique sequences using
346 default settings. Denoising using the Unoise3 algorithm (Edgar, 2016a) was performed to
347 infer amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) from the unique sequences. During this process,
348 chimaeras and singletons (sequences occurring fewer than eight reads across all
349 samples) were removed. Merged reads were subsequently mapped to the resulting ASVs
350 to obtain sample-specific read counts. Taxonomic classification of ASVs was carried out
351 using the SINTAX classifier (Edgar, 2016b) with the RDP training set v19 (Wang and Cole,
352 2024) as the reference database. ASV assigned to *Chloroplast* or representing
353 contaminant DNA, determined by using blanks for DNA extraction, were removed.
354 Contaminants excluded were from the genera *Cutibacterium* and *Lawsonella*, which
355 altogether accounted for less than 0.2% of the reads in the sample. Further, ten samples
356 with a library size below 9,000 reads were excluded from downstream analysis. The final
357 dataset included 111 samples with a median read depth of 100,076 reads. To identify
358 ASVs of the invaders in the dataset, ASVs from Illumina sequencing were aligned to 16S
359 rRNA gene sequences from Sanger sequencing of pure cultures (**Supplementary**
360 **material 1**) using the DECIPHER package (Wright, 2015). ASVs that matched the
361 reference sequences with 100% nucleotide identity and were cross-checked by being
362 highly abundant in the water samples on D0 after the addition of the strains were
363 designated as the invading strains.

364 **Shotgun metagenomic sequencing and processing**

365 We performed shotgun metagenomic sequencing to compare the functional potential of
366 microbiomes from two biofilter groups: a mature control biofilter (Cont_RAS) and a
367 disinfected (perturbed) biofilter (Disf_RAS). Three DNA extracts of biomediated-biofilm

368 samples from each biofilter group collected on D8 were sent to Novogene (Germany) for
369 library preparation, followed by 150 bp paired end shotgun sequencing on Illumina
370 NovaSeq X. The shotgun sequencing data were filtered and deduplicated using fastp
371 v0.23.4 (Chen, 2023). Any reads mapping to the Atlantic salmon or human genomes were
372 removed with Kneaddata v0.12.0 (<https://github.com/biobakery/kneaddata>). After
373 obtaining high-quality reads, we separately assembled metagenome-assembled genomes
374 (MAGs) for each biofilter group using MEGAHIT v1.1.3 (Li et al., 2015) within MetaWRAP
375 v1.3.2 pipeline (Uritskiy et al., 2018). MAGs with less than 70% completeness or above
376 10% contamination as determined by CheckM v1.0.18 (Parks et al., 2015) were excluded
377 from further analysis. We predicted carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes) with the
378 dbCAN database (Zhang et al., 2018).

379 **Data and statistical analysis**

380 Alpha diversity was assessed using Hill numbers of orders 0, 1, and 2, corresponding to
381 observed ASV richness (S), the exponential of Shannon entropy ($\exp H'$), and the inverse
382 Simpson index ($1/D_s$), respectively. To avoid biases associated with rarefied data (see
383 Willis, 2019), diversity indices were estimated via extrapolation (i.e., coverage-based
384 rarefaction and error modelling) using the iNEXT package (Hsieh et al., 2016). The
385 rarefaction analysis with its extrapolation is provided in **Supplementary material 6**.
386 Differences in alpha diversity and beta diversity values over time were analyzed using
387 linear (mixed) models, with sample type, treatment, and sampling point as fixed effects,
388 and bioreactor as a random effect. Three-way ANOVA was used to test the significance
389 of the fixed effects, followed by post hoc pairwise comparisons of estimated marginal
390 means (EMMs) using the emmeans package (Lenth, 2025), with Tukey's adjustment for
391 multiple testing. Residual normality and homoscedasticity of the model and ANOVA were
392 checked. Beta diversities were visualized using principal coordinate analysis (PCoA;
393 Supplementary material 7) and analyzed using permutational multivariate analysis of
394 variance (PERMANOVA; Anderson, 2017), based on Bray–Curtis and Sørensen–Dice
395 dissimilarities. PERMANOVA assumption for homogeneity of multivariate dispersion
396 among groups was tested. Sequencing reads were rarefied for beta diversity analyses
397 based on the Bray-Curtis metric to 46,861 and 52,746 per sample for datasets in Exp1
398 and 2, respectively. Differentially abundant taxa between groups were identified using
399 Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size (LEfSe; Segata et al., 2011), with a minimum LDA
400 score threshold of 4.0. The invasion success of the introduced strains was assessed by
401 their relative abundances in the community on day 8 post-invasion. A p -value ≤ 0.05 was
402 considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed using the R program (R
403 Core Team, 2024) in RStudio (Posit team, 2025). For data wrangling, transformation, and
404 manipulation, the following packages were used: tidyverse (Wickham et al., 2019),
405 phyloseq (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013), microViz (Barnett et al., 2021), and Biostrings
406 (Pagès et al., 2024). The following packages were used for statistical analysis: rstatix
407 (Kassambara, 2023), dunn.test (Dinno, 2024), vegan (Oksanen et al., 2025), and
408 pairwiseAdonis (Martinez Arbizu, 2017). For data visualization and reporting, the following
409 packages were used: ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), ggh4x (Brand, 2024), ggtext (Wilke and
410 Wiernik, 2022), broom (Robinson et al., 2024), and cowplot (Wilke, 2024).

411 **3. Results**

412 **Effect of different disinfectant concentrations on nitrification capacity**

413 We disinfected the biofilter-biomeia to perturb its function and investigate the role of a
 414 mature biofilter in maintaining a healthy microbial environment in RAS. We used a
 415 reduction in nitrification capacity as a proxy of microbial community perturbation due to
 416 disinfection. We evaluated different concentrations of H₂O₂ on nitrification capacity to
 417 determine the appropriate disinfection level that reduces the amount of living biofilm while
 418 maintaining sufficient nitrification capacity to prevent ammonia toxicity in fish. A reactor
 419 with the control biomeia completely converted the ammonia to nitrate and showed no
 420 accumulation of nitrite, indicating a complete nitrification (**Fig. 2A; 2B**). The surface-
 421 specific ammonium and nitrite nitrogen oxidation capacities were 0.13 and 0.14 g N m⁻²
 422 d⁻¹, respectively. The nitrification rate decreased with increasing disinfectant
 423 concentration (**Fig. 2C**). The ratio of the regression slope between control and biomeia
 424 disinfected with 300 mg/L H₂O₂ was 0.015:0.077, suggesting a decrease in nitrification
 425 capacity of 80.5 % (**Fig. 2C**). This concentration was chosen for disinfecting the biomeia
 426 in the experiment carried out in small-scale RAS with salmon fry (Exp1).

427
 428 **Fig. 2** Scatter plots fitted with linear regression showing A) Changes in ammonium (NH₄-N), nitrite
 429 (NO₂-N), and nitrate (NO₃-N) concentrations over time in the batch reactors with mature (non-
 430 disinfected) biomeia spiked with 10 mg N/L of ammonium and B) with 5 mg N/L of nitrite. C)
 431 Ammonium oxidation rate by biomeia in medium with 10 mg N/L of ammonium after being
 432 disinfected at different hydrogen peroxide concentrations. The absolute value of the slopes was
 433 determined by linear regression, representing volumetric oxidation rates in units of mg N L⁻¹ min⁻¹.

434 Water quality in small-scale RAS (Exp1)

435 To examine the potential role of the biofilter in counteracting bacterial invasions in RAS,
 436 we conducted an experiment using a small-scale RAS with salmon fry. Throughout the
 437 eight-day experimental period, water quality variables were generally within the optimal
 438 range for Atlantic salmon fry (**Table 2**). Total ammonia (NH₃ and NH₄⁺) and nitrite
 439 concentrations remained low both in the control RAS (Cont_RAS) and the RAS with
 440 disinfected biofilter-biomeia (Disf_RAS). This was also the case for the nitrate
 441 concentrations, likely due to the low feeding rate and sufficient water exchange (530 L of
 442 new water added per kilogram of feed). The Cont_RAS consistently had no observable
 443 concentrations of total ammonia (**Table 2**). In the Disf_RAS, the total ammonia was

444 observed at low concentrations between 0.2 and 0.5 mg/L, which are still below the
445 recommended thresholds (**Table 2**). This suggested compromised nitrification capacity in
446 the biofilter with disinfected biomed. No fish mortality occurred during the experiment.

447 **Table 2**
 448 Physicochemical water quality shown as the lowest and highest measurement and their average
 449 in brackets, and the recommended range for Atlantic salmon fry (Lekang, 2022)

Variable*	Cont_RAS	Disf_RAS	Recommended range
Dissolved oxygen (mg/L)	8.4–9.6 (9.0)	8.7–9.7 (9.2)	> 7
pH	7.0–7.6 (7.3)	7.3–7.7 (7.5)	6.3–7
Temperature (°C)	11.2–12.4 (11.8)	11.1–11.9 (11.5)	12–14
Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ /L)	55 (59)	55 (71)	
TAN (mg /L)	nd	nd–0.5 (0.2)	< 2
NO ₂ ⁻ (mg/L)	nd	nd–0.25 (0.1)	< 1
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	5–10	0.5–10	< 100

450 *nd = not detected

451 **Effect of disinfection on colonization success by the invaders**

452 In Exp1, we added four rapid-growing, potentially invasive bacterial strains to both the
 453 water of Cont_RAS and Disf_RAS on the experimental day (D0). For biomedial samples
 454 taken before the addition of the strains, the ASVs representing the added *Flavobacterium*,
 455 *Pseudomonas*, *Psychrobacter*, and *Proteus* strains were not observed (**Fig. 3A**). This
 456 confirms that these strains were not established in the biofilters' biofilm before their
 457 addition to the RAS. The water samples taken two hours after addition from both RAS had
 458 a significant proportion of the added strains (**Fig. 3A**). We aimed at adding the four strains
 459 to the same final concentrations; however, their relative abundances varied: the
 460 *Flavobacterium*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Psychrobacter* strains were highly abundant,
 461 accounting for around 9, 25, and 42 % of the total reads, respectively, whereas the *Proteus*
 462 strain was as low as 1.3 % (**Fig. 3A**). As expected due to the dominance of these invaders,
 463 we observed significantly reduced alpha diversity indices compared to any other sample
 464 type at any time point (Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.01$; **Fig. 4A**). These observations confirmed
 465 the introduction of invaders in both Cont_RAS and Disf_RAS.

466 Next, we determined the relative abundance of the ASVs representing the four strains in
 467 the water and biofilter communities eight days after their introduction (D8) as a proxy of
 468 their invasion success. We found that the total proportions of bacterial invaders on D8
 469 were significantly higher in both the biomedial and water samples of the Disf_RAS
 470 compared to those of the Cont_RAS (LEfSe, $p < 0.01$). In the Cont_RAS on D8, the total
 471 proportion of invaders was averaged at 1.55 % and 0.09 % in the tank water and biomedial-
 472 biofilm, respectively (**Fig. 3A**). By contrast, Disf_RAS had 11.68 % and 7.09 %, respectively
 473 (**Fig. 3A**). These results indicate that a greater invasion success in the system
 474 with a perturbed biofilter, whereas having a well-functioning biofilter in the system
 475 counteracted the bacterial invasion in the tank water and biomedial-biofilm. In Disf_RAS,
 476 proportions of *Flavobacterium* sp. and *Pseudomonas* sp. were significantly higher
 477 compared to Cont_RAS (LEfSe, $p < 0.01$; **Fig. 2A**). Their relative abundances in tank
 478 water of Disf_RAS reached 7.4 % and 4.0 %, respectively, and 4.7 % and 2.1 % in
 479 biomedial biofilms (**Fig. 3A**). In contrast, they comprised only 1.4 % and 0.1 % of the tank
 480 water of Cont_RAS and 0.1 % and 0.01 % of the biofilm community. These differences in
 481 relative abundance were substantial, corresponding to approximately 5 and 29 times
 482 higher in water and approximately 59 and 214 times higher in biofilms of Disf_RAS (**Fig.**

483 **3A**). The relative abundances of *Proteus* and *Psychrobacter* strains were low in both
484 Cont_RAS and Disf_RAS and did not differ significantly between systems across sample
485 types (LEfSe, $p > 0.05$; **Fig. 3A**), indicating limited colonization success.

486 In both treatment groups, the invasion success differed between sample types, with a
487 higher success observed in tank water compared to biomedial-biofilm (**Fig. 3A**; LEfSe, $p <$
488 0.01). As described above, the total proportion of the added strains in Cont_RAS was 1.55
489 % in the tank water compared with only 0.09 % in the biomedial-biofilm (**Fig. 3A**). A similar
490 pattern was observed in the Disf_RAS, where strains comprised 11.68 % of the tank water
491 community but only 7.09 % of the biomedial-biofilm (**Fig. 3A**). These results indicate that
492 the biomedial-biofilm had greater resistance to invasion than the tank water. Since the
493 amplicon sequencing data only reflect relative abundances, the increased relative
494 abundances for the added strains in Disf_RAS could be due to the loss of microbial
495 biomass resulting from disinfection. We therefore included clean and autoclaved biomedial
496 ("virgin biomedial", VBm) that were incubated in the biofilters of Cont_RAS and Disf_RAS
497 throughout the experiment and assessed the invasion success for the four added strains.
498 We found that the virgin biomedial in Disf_RAS also had a significantly higher total relative
499 abundance of the added strains (**Fig. 3A**; LEfSe, $p < 0.05$). *Pseudomonas* sp., in
500 particular, had a relative abundance of 4.72 % in Disf_RAS, compared to 0.21 % in
501 Cont_RAS (**Fig. 3A**). This observation supports that invasion success was higher in
502 Disf_RAS.

503 Due to resource constraints, we could not include replicate RAS in Exp1. We therefore
504 followed up on Exp1 by conducting an invasion experiment using laboratory-scale moving-
505 bed bioreactors (MBBRs) (Exp2). Again, the invasion success was higher in the
506 bioreactors running with disinfected biomedial (Disf_MBBR) compared to the bioreactors
507 with mature (non-disinfected) biomedial (Cont_MBBR) (**Fig. 3B**). The total proportion of
508 the strains in Disf_MBBR was 66.9 % in the water and 44.8 % in the biomedial-biofilm
509 communities. In contrast, in the Cont_MBBR, the relative abundances were lower, with
510 16.0 and 8.3 % in the water and biomedial-biofilm, respectively. These observations also
511 suggest that higher invasion success was observed in the MBBRs (Exp2) compared to
512 the RAS (Exp1). Most notably, the relative abundances of *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Proteus*
513 sp. strains in the water communities of Disf_MBBR were as high as 38 % and 11 %
514 respectively (**Fig. 3B**). In comparison, the Cont_MBBR had only 4 % and 0.02 %, respectively
515 (**Fig. 3B**). The invasion success in the water and biomedial-biofilm differed
516 significantly among strains (**Fig. 3B**; LEfSe, $p < 0.05$). For instance, in Disf_MBBR,
517 *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Proteus* sp. were more highly abundant in the tank water (38 %
518 and 11 %, respectively) than in the biomedial-biofilm (1.3 % and 0.5 %, respectively) (**Fig.**
519 **3B**). In contrast, in the same system (Disf_MBBR), *Psychrobacter* sp. and *Flavobacterium*
520 sp. exhibited the opposite trend, being more abundant in the biomedial-biofilm (35 % and
521 1.3 %, respectively) than in the water (17.4 % and 0.05 %, respectively) (**Fig. 3B**). This
522 pattern suggests two distinct lifestyle strategies among these invaders: a predominantly
523 planktonic mode versus a biofilm-associated mode. Overall, the results of Exp2 confirmed
524 those of Exp1.

525
 526 **Fig. 3** The relative abundances of the ASVs representing the added *Flavobacterium*,
 527 *Pseudomonas*, *Psychrobacter*, and *Proteus* strains in the biomedium-biofilm and water at different
 528 time points. A) Invasion experiment in the small-scale RAS (Exp1) and B) in the moving-bed
 529 bioreactors/MBBRs (Exp2). Bm = Biomedium, TW = Tank water in the RAS, W = Water in the
 530 MBBRs, VBm = Virgin biomedium in the RAS, Cont. = Control group, Disf. = Disinfected group, D0
 531 = Day 0. The water sampled on D0 was after the addition of the strains. D8 = Day 8 after the
 532 introduction of the strains to the system. Details about the samples and the number of replicates
 533 are given in Supplementary Material 4.

534 **Effect of disinfection on the microbial community structure in the biomedium and**
 535 **water**

536 Beyond the invasion success for the four added strains, we further examined changes in
 537 the biofilm and water community structure to understand the broader impact of the
 538 perturbed biofilter on the microbial ecology in RAS. Compared to the non-disinfected
 539 biomedium, the biomedium that were immediately sampled from the disinfection bath in Exp1
 540 showed significantly lower Shannon and inverse Simpson diversity (**Fig. 4A**; Tukey's HSD,
 541 $p < 0.01$), but similar observed richness (**Fig. 4A**; Fig. 5; Tukey's HSD, $p = 0.43$). This
 542 suggests that the relative abundances of taxa changed immediately as a direct
 543 consequence of disinfection, while ASV richness remained relatively stable. The decrease
 544 in evenness of the biomedium communities indicated dominance by a few microbial taxa,
 545 possibly those more resistant to disinfection.

546 From D0 to D8, the biomedial-biofilm and the tank water community in both Exp1 and Exp2
547 underwent significant compositional changes (**Supplementary Material 7**;
548 PERMANOVA, $p < 0.05$). Overall, the change was greater when measured using the Bray-
549 Curtis metric compared to the Sørensen-Dice (**Fig. 5**; Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.01$). This
550 suggests that relative abundances changed over time, but the taxa inventory remained
551 relatively stable. Compared to their control, the communities in the disinfected biomedial
552 of Disf_RAS and Disft_MBBR underwent more significant compositional changes after
553 eight days (**Fig. 5**; Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.01$). This is expected and demonstrates the direct
554 effect of disinfection in perturbing the biomedial communities. Compared to their control
555 (Cont_MBBR), the water communities in Disf_MBBR had significantly lower community
556 changes as measured by the Bray-Curtis metric (**Fig. 5B**; Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.01$). This
557 implies that the water communities in Disf_MBBR on D8 were more similar to those in D0,
558 where the strains had just been added.

559 In both treatment groups and experiments, the composition of the water community
560 changed more significantly compared to the biomedial-biofilm communities (**Fig. 5**;
561 Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.01$). This indicates that the biomedial-biofilm community was more
562 stable after disinfection than those in the water column. The biomedial-biofilm communities
563 in Cont_RAS maintained a significantly higher proportion of *Nitrospira* and
564 *Betaproteobacteria* (f: *Comamonadaceae*; g: *Nitrosomonas*) compared to Disf_RAS on
565 day 8 (**Fig. 6**; LEfSe, $p < 0.01$), which may explain their high nitrification capacity observed
566 in the batch experiment. In contrast, biomedial and tank water in Disf_RAS had a
567 significantly higher proportion of *Gammaproteobacteria* and *Flavobacteriia* (**Fig. 6**; LEfSe,
568 $p < 0.01$). The dominant *Gammaproteobacteria* and *Flavobacteriia* were represented by
569 multiple ASVs, not those of the introduced strains (**Fig. 6A**, LEfSe, $p < 0.01$). Interestingly,
570 despite this dominance, the biomedial community in Disf_RAS had higher values for all
571 three alpha diversity indices compared to Cont_RAS (**Fig. 5A**; Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.01$).

572 To understand the differences in functional potential between control biomedial-biofilm
573 communities (Cont_RAS) and disinfected biomedial (Disf_RAS) on D8, we shotgun
574 sequenced samples collected at these time points. We focused on genes associated with
575 carbohydrate metabolism. The biomedial-biofilm community in general had high
576 abundances of genes within the glycosyl transferase and glycoside hydrolase families,
577 while demonstrating a markedly limited presence of genes within the cellulosome family
578 (**Supplementary material 5**; Figure S3). Regarding carbohydrate utilization potential, the
579 biomedial-biofilm communities in Disf_RAS possessed significantly greater numbers of
580 genes within carbohydrate-binding modules and carbohydrate esterase families
581 compared to those in Cont_RAS (**Supplementary material 5**; Figure S3; Welch's test, p
582 < 0.05). No significant differences were observed across other gene families
583 (**Supplementary material 5**; Figure S3; Welch's test, $p > 0.05$).

584 The results of Exp2 generally confirmed those of Exp1. In Exp2, the composition profile
585 revealed that *Gammaproteobacteria* had a significantly higher proportion in the recently
586 disinfected biomedial on D0 (**Fig. 6B**; LEfSe, $p < 0.05$). This indicates a higher resistance
587 of this class to strong disinfection. The composition change in biomedial from D0 to D8
588 of the disinfected group was more pronounced in Exp2 (Disf_MBBR) compared to Exp1
589 (Disf_RAS), indicating a more disturbed biomedial community in Exp2, most likely due to
590 stronger disinfection (**Fig. 5**). The biomedial and water communities in the Disf_MBBR
591 were strongly dominated by *Gammaproteobacteria*, resulting in lower values for all three
592 diversity indices (Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.01$). Unlike Exp1, the dominant

593 *Gammaproteobacteria* in Exp2 were primarily represented by the ASVs of the added
594 strains (**Fig. 6B**).

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595

596 **Fig. 4** Alpha diversity indices of the biomedium-biofilm and water communities on day 0 (D0) and 8 (D8). A) Invasion experiment in the small
 597 laboratory-scale RAS (Exp1) and B) in the semicontinuous moving-bed bioreactors (Exp2). Each dot in the boxplot represents one microbial
 598 community sample. Bm = Biomedium, TW = Tank water in the RAS, W = Water in the MBBRs, VBm = Virgin biomedium in the RAS, Cont. = Control
 599 group, Disf. = Disinfected group, D0 = Day 0. The water sampled on D0 was after the addition of the strains. D8 = Day 8 after the introduction of
 600 the strains to the system. Details about the samples and the number of replicates are given in Supplementary Material 4.

601

602 **Fig. 5** Bray-Curtis and Sørensen-Dice dissimilarities (beta diversity) for comparison of
 603 community composition between the two sampling points, day 0 (D0) and day 8 (D8). A)
 604 Results from the invasion experiment in the small-scale RAS (Exp1) and B) from the invasion
 605 experiment in the semicontinuous moving-bed bioreactors/MBBRs (in Exp2). * = Mean of
 606 values in the boxplot. D0 = Day 0. The water sampled on D0 was after the addition of the
 607 strains. D8 = Day 8 after the introduction of the strains to the system.

A)	Bm; D0		Bm; D8		TW; D0		TW; D8		VBm; D8	
	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.
<i>Unassigned</i>	6.4	5.3	6	5.8	1.3	1.6	5.8	4.5	5.4	4.5
<i>Tepidiformia</i>	0.8	1.1	1.2	0.9	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Subdivision3</i>	1.4	1.5	1	0.6	0.2	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1
<i>Saprospira</i>	17.3	13	10.9	10.1	2.8	1.3	12.9	5.2	1.3	1
<i>Planctomycetia</i>	2.7	2.7	3.6	2	0.6	0.5	1.7	0.9	1.5	1.4
<i>Parcubacteria_incertae</i>	2.2	1.7	1.5	0.7	0.4	0.2	4.5	1.8	0	0
<i>Nitrospira</i>	17	23.7	22.2	9	0.7	0.3	1.1	0.5	0.3	0.1
<i>Gemmatimonadia</i>	1.6	2.1	1.1	1.5	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.1	0.5
<i>Gammaproteobacteria*</i>	0	0	0	2.4	75.9	63.8	0.2	4	0.2	4.2
<i>Gammaproteobacteria</i>	2.7	2.8	2.5	11.9	1.3	1.6	5.2	15.9	1.7	3.9
<i>Flavobacteriia*</i>	0	0	0.1	5.3	6.3	9.1	1.4	7.5	4.1	5.4
<i>Flavobacteriia</i>	2.5	2.8	3.9	6.7	0.5	2.5	9.2	11.1	26	10.3
<i>Deltaproteobacteria</i>	3.4	4	3.3	3	0.3	0.4	1.3	1.7	0.4	0.6
<i>Cytophagia</i>	2.9	2.6	3.1	2.3	0.9	0.9	2.9	1.9	3.2	1.6
<i>Chitinophagia</i>	2.8	2.2	3.8	2.9	0.8	0.6	3.7	2.4	3	1.6
<i>Caldilineae</i>	1.2	0.9	1.7	0.9	0.3	0.2	0.9	0.5	0.2	0.5
<i>Betaproteobacteria</i>	8.2	7.6	7.6	5.8	2.2	5.8	28	12.2	31.5	31.8
<i>Bacilli</i>	1.9	2.1	2.2	2	0.2	0.5	1.2	0.9	0.7	1.7
<i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>	14.9	14	17.4	16.6	2.9	6.6	13.6	18.3	16.1	21
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	2.3	2.1	1.5	1.6	0.4	0.5	1.4	1.4	1.3	2
<i>Acidobacteria_Gp6</i>	0.9	1.6	1.1	1	0.5	1.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0
≤2%	5.2	4.4	4.8	5.8	1.2	2.1	5	7.2	2.8	6.2

B)	Bm; D0		Bm; D8		W; D0	W; D8	
	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.		Cont.	Disf.
<i>Unassigned</i>	8.2	6.9	2.6	1	0	1.9	0
<i>Sphingobacteriia</i>	0	0	2.6	0	0	13.3	0
<i>Planctomycetia</i>	1.6	1.9	0.7	0.4	0	0.2	0
<i>Nitrospira</i>	31.8	33.7	24.3	2.4	0	0.6	0
<i>Gemmatimonadia</i>	3.7	2	1.2	0	0	0.5	0
<i>Gammaproteobacteria*</i>	0	0	8.3	40.6	75.4	13.8	70
<i>Gammaproteobacteria</i>	1.9	3	3.2	2.4	0.2	7.1	2.6
<i>Flavobacteriia*</i>	0	0	0.1	1.2	24.5	0.4	0
<i>Flavobacteriia</i>	0.1	0.2	1	0.5	0	2.1	0
<i>Deltaproteobacteria</i>	3.7	4.3	0.7	0.2	0	0.2	0
<i>Chloroflexia</i>	1.4	0.6	0.3	0.1	0	0.2	0
<i>Chitinophagia</i>	0.2	0.3	1.5	0	0	4.2	0
<i>Caldilineae</i>	0.6	2.4	0.7	1	0	0.6	0
<i>Betaproteobacteria</i>	6.5	7.1	16.5	4.4	0	22.7	1.5
<i>Bacilli</i>	0	0	0.6	28.8	0	2	11.7
<i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>	20.8	21.4	25.4	5.9	0	25.8	11
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	3.9	3.4	2.6	3.6	0	1.1	2.3
<i>Acidobacteria_Gp6</i>	3.8	2.6	1.6	0	0	0.3	0
<i>Acidobacteria_Gp16</i>	1.2	1	0.3	0.4	0	0	0
<i>Acidobacteria_Gp10</i>	1.6	1.9	0.3	0.1	0	0.1	0
≤2%	5.7	6	2.6	0.5	0	1.5	0

608

609 **Fig. 6** Composition at the class level of biomed-ia-biofilm and water communities at different time points. A) Invasion experiment in the small
610 laboratory-scale RAS (Exp1) and B) in the semicontinuous moving-bed bioreactors (Exp2). Classes with maximum abundance lower than 2% in
611 any sample were summed to the “<2 %” category. Bm = Biomed-ia, TW = Tank water in the RAS, W = Water in the MBBRs, VBm = Virgin
612 biomed-ia in the RAS, Cont. = Control group, Disf. = Disinfected group, D0 = Day 0. The water sampled on D0 was after the addition of the strains.

613 D8 = Day 8 after the introduction of the strains to the system. The asterisk (*) after *Gammaproteobacteria* and *Flavobacteria* represents the added
614 strains.

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615 4. Discussion

616 The most recognized biofilter function in RAS is to facilitate nitrification, thereby
617 maintaining low ammonia and nitrite concentrations in the system. We previously
618 hypothesized that a well-functioning biofilter would have an additional function:
619 maintaining a positive microbial environment for fish (Attramadal et al., 2014; De
620 Schryver and Vadstein, 2014). In this study, we tested whether a mature biofilter would
621 counteract bacterial invasion by securing strong competition for resources in the
622 system. We further expected that this strong resource competition would also
623 suppress the growth of rapid-growing heterotrophs, which are potentially detrimental
624 to fish.

625 We observed marked differences in microbial community structure in the rearing water
626 and biomedica of systems in which the biofilter was perturbed by disinfection. On day
627 8 (D8) in both experiments, the added strains showed significantly higher relative
628 abundance, i.e., colonization success, in systems with a perturbed biofilter than in
629 systems with a mature biofilter. This observation suggests that a mature biofilter can
630 counteract bacterial invasion by rapid-growing potentially pathogenic heterotrophs.
631 Additionally, we observed a reduced relative abundance of the classes
632 *Gammaproteobacteria* and *Flavobacteria* (excluding the invaders) in the rearing water
633 of systems with a mature biofilter. This indicates that, besides counteracting bacterial
634 invasion, a mature biofilter also suppresses the growth of rapid-growing heterotrophs.
635 The increased invasion success and bloom of heterotrophs observed in the system
636 with a perturbed biofilter align with hypotheses proposed in earlier work (De Schryver
637 and Vadstein, 2014; Vadstein et al., 2018) and are consistent with the r/K selection
638 theory (Andrews and Harris, 1986; Pianka, 1970). In brief, biomedica disinfection
639 reduced bacterial biomass without reducing carrying capacity (space and dissolved
640 organic substrates), creating unoccupied niches in the system and reduced
641 competition among bacterial populations. These conditions increased the colonization
642 success of the added strains and favored the proliferation of rapid-growing r-strategists
643 with high maximum growth rates (Yin et al., 2022; Pianka, 1970). By contrast, in both
644 experiments control systems with a mature biofilter resisted invasion and suppressed
645 the proliferation of rapid-growing bacteria. In the mature biomedica-biofilm, a lower
646 invasion success was likely due to competitive exclusion caused by the resident
647 bacteria (Nadell et al., 2015). Resident biofilm bacteria likely consume the dissolved
648 organic matter in the rearing water, thereby reducing nutrient availability that would
649 otherwise promote the bloom of planktonic r-strategists.

650 Shotgun sequencing showed that the biomedica-biofilm community, in general, had
651 high abundances of genes within the glycosyl transferase (GT) and glycoside
652 hydrolase (GH) families, but limited abundances within the cellulosome family. The
653 prevalence of GT and GH is consistent with their ubiquitous and fundamental function
654 in biofilm structure. For instance, GTs are involved in synthesizing the complex
655 polysaccharides that form the matrix of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS),
656 which is a structural backbone of the biofilm (Rainey et al., 2018). The limited
657 cellulosome genes suggest that the communities were not well adapted to
658 metabolizing the cellulose substrate, most likely due to the limited amount in the RAS.
659 Cellulose is not digestible to fish and represents only a minor fraction in the feed as
660 part of the use of plant-based ingredients (Sinha et al., 2011). Compared to
661 Cont_RAS, the biomedica-biofilm communities in Disf_RAS had significantly more

662 genes encoding carbohydrate-binding modules and carbohydrate esterase families.
663 Immediately after disinfection, we observed biofilm detachment from the biomed. We
664 speculate that a higher prevalence of these genes may relate to biofilm conditioning
665 and recovery, e.g., recreation of new biofilm biomass after disinfection. Overall, these
666 findings suggest that disinfection not only changed the taxonomic composition of the
667 RAS biofilter microbiome but also altered its ecological function within RAS.

668 We observed reduced Shannon and inverse Simpson diversity in samples with higher
669 invasion success and higher relative abundance of rapid-growing bacteria, particularly
670 in Exp2. This pattern is expected because the dominance of a few taxa lowers
671 community evenness, which would be reflected in the decrease in diversity indices
672 that consider evenness. Reduced diversity is therefore often used as an indicator of
673 dysbiosis in aquaculture systems (Infante-Villamil et al., 2021). For instance, reduced
674 diversity in water microbiota in RAS has been associated with poor microbial water
675 quality for the fish, as it is linked to blooms of opportunistic bacteria (Vestrum et al.,
676 2018). In contrast, an evenly composed community often indicates a resilient and
677 functional system due to functional redundancy as observed in the gut microbiota
678 (Louca et al., 2018). However, we found that evenness in biofilm communities did not
679 reflect biofilter performance. Lower evenness does not necessarily indicate a
680 perturbed biofilter; likewise, high evenness alone may not demonstrate a well-
681 functioning biofilter. In our Exp1, the biomed-biofilm community of Cont_RAS on D8
682 showed lower evenness than Disf_RAS. Composition profiles revealed a high relative
683 abundance, i.e., dominance by *Nitrospira*, which explains the lower evenness. Rather
684 than dysbiosis, this dominance indicated a well-adapted community optimized for
685 nitrification, which is desirable in biofilters. This finding cautions against relying solely
686 on diversity to indicate dysbiosis in RAS, because selective enrichment of functionally
687 essential taxa can also lead to lower evenness. For a more accurate assessment, it is
688 necessary to integrate functional and compositional profiles and consider the
689 ecological function of the system in question.

690 We observed that the composition of the biomed-biofilm communities was less
691 affected by disinfection than the communities in the water column in both experiments.
692 Bacteria growing embedded in biofilms are known to be more protected than their
693 planktonic counterparts. The resistance is partly due to the EPS matrix shielding the
694 community from environmental changes or stressors (Hall and Mah, 2017; Singh et
695 al., 2021). In Exp2, we showed that the biomed disinfection with H₂O₂ immediately
696 led to an increase in the relative abundance of the class *Gammaproteobacteria* in the
697 biomed-biofilm. This aligns with studies showing greater persistence of members of
698 this class following routine disinfection in slaughterhouses (Naim et al., 2025). Given
699 that 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing cannot determine cell viability (i.e., cannot
700 distinguish live from dead cells), this observation may be attributed to biofilm
701 detachment, as we observed biofilm shedding during disinfection. The relative
702 increase in *Gammaproteobacteria* may indicate their greater persistence within the
703 biofilm matrix compared to the nitrifiers, which were lost through detachment because
704 of their predominance in the outer aerobic layers (Gieseke et al., 2001). Next, we
705 observed a more pronounced bloom of rapid-growing bacteria and higher colonization
706 success in the semicontinuous moving-bed bioreactors (Exp2) compared to the small-
707 scale RAS (Exp1). This may be explained by (1) a higher disinfectant dose, causing
708 higher mortality in the biomed-biofilm, i.e., a reduced number of bacterial cells, and
709 subsequently a larger gap between bacterial numbers and carrying capacity; and (2)

710 a higher water exchange rate and a more open, dynamic system in the RAS
711 experiment, compared to semicontinuous reactor systems.

712 Our findings should have significant practical and economic implications for
713 aquaculture operations and authorities when considering the implementation of
714 routine biofilter disinfection. The increased invasion success in disinfected biofilms
715 suggests that the biofilter may have a higher risk of being colonized by opportunistic
716 or disease-specific bacteria during the early stages of community succession. As the
717 species living in the biofilm are relatively persistent, the colonizing bacteria may be
718 released to the rearing water as the biofilter sheds the biofilm. Furthermore, the direct
719 deterioration in microbial quality i.e., increased growth of fast-growing heterotrophic
720 bacteria in the rearing water and biomedial-biofilm after the biofilter perturbation implies
721 that fish can be exposed to opportunistic and or pathogenic bacteria as they are also
722 typically r-strategists. Fish are vulnerable during the interval between the perturbation
723 and the re-establishment of a stable microbial community, regardless of the duration
724 of this interval. The persistence of the *Gammaproteobacteria* within the biofilm
725 suggests that suboptimal biofilter disinfection may lead to the loss of beneficial taxa
726 such as *Nitrospira*, while retaining more resilient taxa like *Gammaproteobacteria*, class
727 which host many genera associated with aquaculture pathogens.

728 Loss of nitrification capacity is the most apparent consequence of biofilter disinfection
729 (Qi et al., 2025) and could lead to decreased production. Farmers may need to reduce
730 the feed load to control ammonia concentrations in the system, consequently losing
731 growth potential. Moreover, because nitrifying bacteria grow more slowly than
732 heterotrophs, recovery of nitrification after total disinfection requires considerable time.
733 This delay may result in production downtime and associated economic losses.
734 Alternatively, to maintain the existing production level, farmers may require an
735 investment in dedicated biomedial maturation units for biofilter seeding, which can
736 accelerate biofilter recovery (Navada et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2016). Screening of the
737 biofilm for pathogens and avoiding disinfection in case of negative results should be
738 evaluated as an alternative to mandatory disinfection. Finally, future studies should
739 assess the long-term impact and recovery of biofilters following disinfection.
740 Nevertheless, this study demonstrated that even within a short time frame, immediate
741 effects were observed on microbial community succession, with an increase in
742 invasion success and in the proportion of rapid-growing heterotrophic bacteria.

743 5. Conclusion

744 This study demonstrates that a mature biofilter in RAS significantly reduces the
745 invasion success of rapid-growing bacterial strains and promotes a healthier microbial
746 environment associated with lower relative abundances of rapid-growing heterotrophic
747 classes *Gammaproteobacteria* and *Flavobacteriia*, which are potentially detrimental to
748 fish. Conversely, systems with a perturbed biofilter exhibited a higher invasion success
749 and were repopulated by rapid-growing heterotrophic bacteria. This indicates that the
750 mature biofilter may also protect the system against invasions by pathogenic species,
751 as they are often also characterized by fast-growing heterotrophic bacteria. Our
752 findings highlight the often-overlooked role of RAS biofilters in maintaining a positive
753 microbial environment for fish. Understanding the consequences of biofilter
754 perturbation beyond just nitrification loss is crucial for developing microbial
755 management strategies in RAS, especially as biosecurity concerns increase. We
756 advise avoiding routine biofilter disinfection as a disease-prevention measure in RAS.

757 Further work is needed to link the biofilter perturbations with host welfare. Overall, this
758 study offers new insights into the biofilter's function in optimizing the microbial
759 environment in RAS, emphasizing its effects on microbial community dynamics and
760 the invasion success by rapid-growing heterotrophic bacteria.

761 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

762 Fernando Fernando: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation,
763 Data Curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. Sujan Khadka: Methodology,
764 Investigation, Writing – review & editing. Simen Fredriksen: Formal analysis, Writing –
765 review & editing, Kristine Hofstad: Investigation, Writing – review & editing. Olav
766 Vadstein: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing,
767 Supervision, Funding acquisition. Ingrid Bakke: Conceptualization, Methodology,
768 Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding
769 acquisition.

770 **Declaration of competing interest**

771 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
772 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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782 **Data availability**

783 All amplicon sequencing data generated in this study are available on NCBI with an
784 accession ID of PRJNA1298933. The metadata describing the sample type, treatment
785 group, and other relevant information is provided in **Supplementary material 5**.

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987 **Appendix A. PCR protocol for colony PCR**

988 **Table A1**

989 The reagent mixture used in the colony PCR

Reagents	Final concentration	Volume
PCR grade H ₂ O	-	Up to 25 μ L
5 \times Phusion buffer HF (7.5 mM MgCl ₂)	1 \times	5.0 μ L
Forward Primer Eub-8F (10 μ M)	0.3 μ M	0.75 μ L
Reverse Primer 1492R (10 μ M)	0.3 μ M	0.75 μ L
dNTP (10 mM each)	250 μ M each	0.625 μ L
Phusion Hot Start DNA polymerase (2 units/ μ L)	0.02 units/ μ L	0.18 μ L

990

991 **Table A2**

992 Temperature and cycling conditions used in the colony PCR for amplification of the 16S rRNA
993 gene

Step	Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	Time (seconds)	Number of cycles
Pre-denaturation	98	120	1
Denaturation	98	15	
Annealing	55	20	35
Elongation	72	20	
Final elongation	72	300	1

994

995 **Appendix B. Composition of ammonium and nitrite medium**

996 **Table B1**

997 Chemical composition of the ammonium medium (concentration of 10 mg/L) used for
 998 determining the ammonia oxidation capacity

Chemical	Quantity (g/L)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	0.04717
$\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.272
Na_2CO_3	0.2
Trace metal solution	10 mL of stock solution
pH adjustment	3–6 drops of HCl to pH 7.5

999

1000 **Table B2**

1001 Chemical composition of the nitrite medium (concentration of 5 mg/L) used for determining the
 1002 nitrite oxidation capacity

Chemical	Quantity (g/L)
$\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.272
Na_2CO_3	1
NaNO_2	0.0242
Trace metal solution	10 mL
pH adjustment	3–6 drops of HCl to pH 7.5

1003

1004 **Table B3**

1005 Chemical composition of the trace metal solution

Chemical	Quantity (g/L)
$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.5
$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.5
$\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.2
$\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.55
ZnCl_2	0.07
$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.12
$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.12
EDTA; Tridriplex III	2.8

1006

1007 **Appendix C. Composition of M65 medium**

1008 **Table C**

1009 Composition of 10× M65 medium used as a nutrient source in the invasion trial in reactors
1010 (Exp2)

Ingredient	g/L distilled water
Yeast extract	5
Bacteriological peptone	5
Tryptone	5

1011

1012 **Appendix D. Supplementary Materials**

- 1013 Supplementary material 1 16S rRNA gene sequences of the bacterial invaders.
- 1014 Supplementary material 2 Dataset of morphological characteristics (Sheet 1), CFU-
1015 OD (Sheet2-6), and cell number-OD relationship (Sheet 7) of the bacteria used as
1016 invaders.
- 1017 Supplementary material 3 Time series of nitrogenous compound measurements
1018 during the batch experiment to evaluate nitrification capacity.
- 1019 Supplementary material 4 Tabulation of sequenced and analyzed samples in this
1020 study.
- 1021 Supplementary material 5 Metadata describing relevant information for each amplicon
1022 sequencing library uploaded to the NCBI repository.
- 1023 Supplementary material 6 Rarefaction and extrapolation curves for alpha diversity
1024 analysis for all sequencing libraries generated in this study.
- 1025 Supplementary material 7 PCoA and results of the pairwise PERMANOVA test to
1026 evaluate microbial community composition between sample groups.

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Compound: ● NH₄⁺-N ● NO₂⁻-N ● NO₃⁻²-N

[H₂O₂]: ● Control ● 300 mg/L ● 600 mg/L ● 1,200 mg/L

A) Day 0

Day 8

B) Day 0

Day 8

Treatment: Cont. (Green), Dis. (Red), Shared (Yellow)

A)

	Bm; D0		Bm; D8		TW; D0		TW; D8		VBm; D8	
	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.
<i>Unassigned</i>	6.4	5.3	6	5.8	1.3	1.6	5.8	4.5	5.4	4.5
<i>Tepidiformia</i>	0.8	1.1	1.2	0.9	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Subdivision3</i>	1.4	1.5	1	0.6	0.2	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1
<i>Saprospira</i>	17.3	13	10.9	10.1	2.8	1.3	12.9	5.2	1.3	1
<i>Planctomycetia</i>	2.7	2.7	3.6	2	0.6	0.5	1.7	0.9	1.5	1.4
<i>Parcubacteria_incertae</i>	2.2	1.7	1.5	0.7	0.4	0.2	4.5	1.8	0	0
<i>Nitrospira</i>	17	23.7	22.2	9	0.7	0.3	1.1	0.5	0.3	0.1
<i>Gemmatimonadia</i>	1.6	2.1	1.1	1.5	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.1	0.5
<i>Gammaproteobacteria*</i>	0	0	0	2.4	75.9	63.8	0.2	4	0.2	4.2
<i>Gammaproteobacteria</i>	2.7	2.8	2.5	11.9	1.3	1.6	5.2	15.9	1.7	3.9
<i>Flavobacteriia*</i>	0	0	0.1	5.3	6.3	9.1	1.4	7.5	4.1	5.4
<i>Flavobacteriia</i>	2.5	2.8	3.9	6.7	0.5	2.5	9.2	11.1	26	10.3
<i>Deltaproteobacteria</i>	3.4	4	3.3	3	0.3	0.4	1.3	1.7	0.4	0.6
<i>Cytophagia</i>	2.9	2.6	3.1	2.3	0.9	0.9	2.9	1.9	3.2	1.6
<i>Chitinophagia</i>	2.8	2.2	3.8	2.9	0.8	0.6	3.7	2.4	3	1.6
<i>Caldilineae</i>	1.2	0.9	1.7	0.9	0.3	0.2	0.9	0.5	0.2	0.5
<i>Betaproteobacteria</i>	8.2	7.6	7.6	5.8	2.2	5.8	28	12.2	31.5	31.8
<i>Bacilli</i>	1.9	2.1	2.2	2	0.2	0.5	1.2	0.9	0.7	1.7
<i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>	14.9	14	17.4	16.6	2.9	6.6	13.6	18.3	16.1	21
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	2.3	2.1	1.5	1.6	0.4	0.5	1.4	1.4	1.3	2
<i>Acidobacteria_Gp6</i>	0.9	1.6	1.1	1	0.5	1.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0
$\leq 2\%$	5.2	4.4	4.8	5.8	1.2	2.1	5	7.2	2.8	6.2

B)

	Bm; D0		Bm; D8		W; D0	W; D8	
	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Disf.	Cont.	Cont.	Disf.
<i>Unassigned</i>	8.2	6.9	2.6	1	0	1.9	0
<i>Sphingobacteriia</i>	0	0	2.6	0	0	13.3	0
<i>Planctomycetia</i>	1.6	1.9	0.7	0.4	0	0.2	0
<i>Nitrospira</i>	31.8	33.7	24.3	2.4	0	0.6	0
<i>Gemmatimonadia</i>	3.7	2	1.2	0	0	0.5	0
<i>Gammaproteobacteria*</i>	0	0	8.3	40.6	75.4	13.8	70
<i>Gammaproteobacteria</i>	1.9	3	3.2	2.4	0.2	7.1	2.6
<i>Flavobacteriia*</i>	0	0	0.1	1.2	24.5	0.4	0
<i>Flavobacteriia</i>	0.1	0.2	1	0.5	0	2.1	0
<i>Deltaproteobacteria</i>	3.7	4.3	0.7	0.2	0	0.2	0
<i>Chloroflexia</i>	1.4	0.6	0.3	0.1	0	0.2	0
<i>Chitinophagia</i>	0.2	0.3	1.5	0	0	4.2	0
<i>Caldilineae</i>	0.6	2.4	0.7	1	0	0.6	0
<i>Betaproteobacteria</i>	6.5	7.1	16.5	4.4	0	22.7	1.5
<i>Bacilli</i>	0	0	0.6	28.8	0	2	11.7
<i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>	20.8	21.4	25.4	5.9	0	25.8	11
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	3.9	3.4	2.6	3.6	0	1.1	2.3
<i>Acidobacteria_Gp6</i>	3.8	2.6	1.6	0	0	0.3	0
<i>Acidobacteria_Gp16</i>	1.2	1	0.3	0.4	0	0	0
<i>Acidobacteria_Gp10</i>	1.6	1.9	0.3	0.1	0	0.1	0
$\leq 2\%$	5.7	6	2.6	0.5	0	1.5	0